

Application of Kahoot Game Application Based Assessment in Class Discussion Learning Model Action to Improve Students' Arabic Learning Outcomes

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Abstract

The more advanced the times, the more sophisticated the development of technology. No exception to the technology that should be utilized as much as possible by educators in teaching and learning activities in the classroom possible by educators in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. One of them is of which is that educators can apply the Kahoot application as an assessment tool for learning in the classroom as an effort to create a learning atmosphere so that learning in the classroom as an effort to create a conducive learning atmosphere and conducive and save time in the process of assessing student learning outcomes. This research aims to overcome the problems that occur in the classroom during teaching and learning activities classroom when teaching and learning activities take place as an action taken to improve students' learning outcomes. to improve the learning outcomes of Arabic language of class X students by applying Kahoot game-based assessment in the action model. Kahoot game-based assessment in the action of Class Discussion learning model. This research uses the Classroom Action Research (PTK) method which was implemented in SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setiabudi Pamulang, South Tangerang. This research was conducted in two cycles. First, the pre-cycle stage and cycle 1 in its implementation using the Classroom Discussion learning model which learning model consisting of 5 phases (Clarifying the purpose and establishing the set. Focusing the Discussion, Controlling the Discussion, Ending the Discussion). Discussion, Controlling Discussion, Ending Discussion, Debriefing) The results of the study found that students' Arabic language learning outcomes The pre-cycle stage to the cycle 1 stage, the completeness of student learning outcomes only reached 47% while the cycle 1 stage the completeness of student learning outcomes has increased. Motivation of students to learn and foster the spirit of challenged students to participate in classroom learning activities

Keywords: Class Discussion Learning Model, Kahoot Application, Learning Results

Abstrak

Semakin majunya zaman, semakin canggih pula perkembangan teknologinya. Tak terkecuali teknologi yang sudah seharusnya dimanfaatkan semaksimal mungkin oleh para pendidik dalam kegiatan belajar mengajar di kelas mungkin dilakukan oleh pendidik dalam kegiatan belajar mengajar di kelas. Salah satunya adalah para pendidik dapat menerapkan aplikasi Kahoot sebagai alat penilaian pembelajaran di kelas sebagai upaya menciptakan suasana belajar sehingga pembelajaran di kelas sebagai upaya menciptakan suasana belajar yang kondusif dan kondusif serta aman waktu dalam proses penilaian hasil belajar siswa. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengatasi permasalahan yang terjadi di kelas pada saat kegiatan belajar mengajar. kelas pada saat kegiatan belajar mengajar berlangsung sebagai suatu tindakan yang dilakukan untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar siswa untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar bahasa Arab siswa kelas X dengan menerapkan penilaian berbasis permainan Kahoot pada model tindakan. Penilaian berbasis permainan Kahoot pada tindakan model pembelajaran Diskusi Kelas. Penelitian ini menggunakan metode Penelitian Tindakan Kelas (PTK) yang dilaksanakan di SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setiabudi Pamulang, Tangerang Selatan. Penelitian ini dilakukan dalam dua siklus. Pertama, tahap prasiklus dan siklus 1 dalam pelaksanaannya menggunakan model pembelajaran Diskusi Kelas yang model pembelajarannya terdiri dari 5 fase (Memperjelas tujuan dan memantapkan himpunan, Memfokuskan Pembahasan, Mengontrol Pembahasan, Mengakhiri Pembahasan). Diskusi, Diskusi Pengendalian, Diskusi Akhir, Pembekalan) Hasil penelitian diperoleh bahwa hasil belajar bahasa Arab siswa tahap pra siklus sampai tahap siklus Pertama, ketuntasan hasil belajar siswa hanya mencapai 47% sedangkan pada tahap siklus 1 ketuntasan hasil belajar siswa mengalami peningkatan. Motivasi belajar siswa dan menumbuhkan semangat siswa tertantang untuk mengikuti kegiatan pembelajaran di kelas

Kata Kunci: Model Pembelajaran Diskusi Kelas, Penerapan Kahoot, Hasil Belajar

Introduction

Discussion is the medium through which much teaching takes place and through which students demonstrate to the teacher how much of what they have learned. Discussion provides a means for students to talk about what they already know and to form meaning from the new knowledge acquired. Discussions influence students' thought processes and give them their identity as learners and as members of a class group.

With the application of class discussion learning assessment innovation and Kahoot game application-based assessment in Arabic language learning, it is expected to be empirical evidence for teachers in adopting the class discussion learning model and Kahoot game application-based assessment in their classroom learning to be effective and efficient. The theoretical support of discussion mostly comes from the field of language, communicative process and exchange of ideas or opinions.

With the application of this class discussion learning model, it is also intended that students think more, it also provides opportunities for students to listen to their own thoughts

and to learn how to monitor their own thinking processes. Thus students do not only acquire knowledge by recording new information in notebooks.

Arabic language is a difficult subject according to most students both in formal schools and in non-formal education. Therefore, Arabic language teachers must rectify this wrong assumption by making various innovations that facilitate students' understanding of learning Arabic. Among the efforts that can be made by Arabic language teachers include: 1) instill a happy attitude first in students about Arabic. 2) being able to design Arabic lessons in a fun way. 3) the existence of Language games that need to be done between lessons, if it is felt that the Arabic language material at that time feels boring.(Arifin, A.(2017)

Arabic language skills and a positive attitude towards Arabic is very important in helping to understand the source of Islamic teachings, namely the Qur'an and Hadith and Arabic books related to Islam for learners. Arabic books related to Islam for students.(Kurnia, N.(2018)

Discussion is a social setting where teachers can help students analyze their thinking process and learn important communication skills such as formulating ideas clearly, listening to each other, responding to their friends in an appropriate way, learning how to ask good questions.

Class discussion can be an option, one of the learning models that are student centered learning model that can make the dynamics of learning in learning dynamics in the classroom become more lively. The teacher acts as a designer, facilitator, motivator, and evaluator of the discussion results. Through this model, the teacher can also can show their creativity in a richer, structured, mature, and explorative. Discussion in the context of classroom learning, is a process of exchanging ideas between teachers and students or between students and other students. other students.(Putri, A(2019)

The teacher must hold the students' attention throughout the course, as their attention begins to wane after the first ten minutes of the course. begins to wane after the first ten minutes of the course. The teacher needs to change the environment and engage students to regain their attention. Kahoot! is a free assessment program that can be used at any point in the lesson to increase students to the lesson by the teacher and can also be used as a formative assessment. Kahoot! plays an important role in gamifying a simple assessment program and contributes to the success of learners at various levels.(Sibel, H.(2018)

The purpose of this study is to improve students' Arabic learning outcomes in the action of class discussion learning model and Kahoot game application-based assessment and to analyze the impact of the application of class discussion learning model and Kahoot application-based assessment on students' Arabic learning outcomes in class X IPS 1 at SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setiabudi Pamulang, South Tangerang.

Assessment is an activity in the learning process that aims to obtain and analyze data related to student learning outcomes that are carried out continuously using certain learning evaluation standards, so as to obtain information that is useful in making decisions.(Indriastuti, L. (2022)

Kahoot! plays an important role in improving students' academic performance, motivation and engagement during distance teaching and learning. The continued use of Kahoot as a game-based learning platform appears to improve students' overall academic performance as evidenced by the results obtained in subsequent quizzes. In addition, the use of Kahoot provides opportunities for students to actively engage and work collaboratively as a community of practice.

Collaborative and interactive discussions became a source of motivation for students to learn. As a formative assessment tool, Kahoot served to assist students to achieve the set learning outcomes and provided valuable insights into widespread knowledge gaps. The use of Kahoot as a game-based learning platform provides a meaningful opportunity to adequately address widening knowledge gaps.(Luhando, D. (2022)

Assessment of student learning can be done both through the process and product of student performance. Assessment of student learning outcomes is carried out based on learning objectives (Hermawan, C. M., Rosfiani, O. (2018) R&H classroom action research model. Jakarta: Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia). Teachers can independently assign students to access literature sources from various online platforms (Hermawan, C. M., Rosfiani, O. (2018). R&H classroom action research model. Jakarta: Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia).

Evaluation using the Kahoot application helps motivate and provoke enthusiasm for learning through evaluations that are not monotonous but interesting.(Hidayat, R. (2021) The results showed that with the Kahoot application, students were like playing while learning. The utilization of technology through the Kahoot application, can make the implementation of learning evaluations optimal and help students to better understand Mathematics appropriately. The motivation, enthusiasm and excitement of students in Mathematics lessons multiply with the existence of an online device system with a ranking system. So that the abilities and cognition of students are trained quickly and fun.(Hidayat, R. (2021)

The application of the Kahoot application in HOTS-based cognitive assessment can be an alternative to make it easier for educators to measure the cognitive level of students. The Kahoot application has several important roles, namely the kahoot application provides comprehensive quiz results, and the Kahoot application can measure cognitive levels with HOTS questions and innovations in HOTS-based cognitive assessment, the advantages of Kahoot are that students pay more attention to the educator when delivering material so that they can answer questions using the Kahoot application, create a competitive attitude in class, time restrictions so that students are serious about working on questions, and educators are made easier to get the results of students' work.(Salfadilah, F.(2023)

Several studies have shown that the application of Kahoot game application can increase student activeness in participating in learning. Busiri's research (2020) states that in the discussion of research about the utilization of kahoot media for learning Arabic listening skills listening skills at IAI Sunan Kalijogo Malang, namely the process of improving the ability of students as learning subjects who actively practice the use of Kahoot media.

Effective learning begins in a student-centered environment and will succeed if given the opportunity through students and will succeed if given the opportunity through activities in the utilization of kahoot media, if they participate they will more easily master what they have learned. The use of kahoot media utilization has a very important role in learning Arabic with the support of previously prepared facilities.(Busiri, A.(2020)

The training participants actively tried to understand the concept and implementation of using Kahoot! application in fun learning in the form of quizzes according to the subjects they teach. The results of the analysis showed that the teachers gave a positive response to the training activities on the utilization of Kahoot! utilization of game-based learning media with Kahoot.(Sukmawati, R.Ati.(2022)

Analysis of the data obtained during the research process can be drawn conclusion that from each variable measured, namely learning outcomes, process skills, and students' interest in learning after the implementation of Kahoot educational game Kahoot educational game there is a significant increase in each cycle. cycle. The results of the increase were due to several factors in the learning process, among others, the use of Kahoot Kahoot educational game. The use of the Kahoot game can certainly help students in solving problems related to the evaluation of rational and irrational inequalities of one variable.(Wigati, S.(2019)

Research Focus, Based on the background of the problems presented, the focus of this research is "The Application of Kahoot Game Application-Based Assessment in the Action of Class Discussion Learning Model to Improve Arabic Learning Outcomes of Class X Students at SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setibudi Pamulang.

From the research focus above, the researchers tried to detail the research sub-focus as follows:

A. Application of class discussion learning model and Kahoot game application-based assessment in learning Arabic in class X IPS 1 at SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setiabudi Pamulang, South Tangerang.

B. Learning outcomes of Arabic subject through the application of class discussion learning model and Kahoot game application-based assessment in class X IPS 1 students at SMA Muhammadiyah 25 Setiabudi Pamulang, South Tangerang.

Research Method

This research is a type of Classroom Action Research or the term in English is Classroom Action Research (CAR). Classroom Action Research or PTK is a scientific activity carried out by teachers or observers in the classroom with stages of designing, implementing, observing and reflecting on actions through several cycles in a collaborative and participatory manner that aims to improve or improve the quality of the learning process in the classroom.(Kesume, G.C ,Fauziyah, A. (2016)

Classroom action research is a variety of learning research classroom context that is carried out by teachers to solve learning problems faced by teachers, improve the quality of learning problems faced by teachers, improve the quality and results of learning and try new

things in learning for the sake of and learning outcomes and try new things in learning for the sake of improvement of quality and learning outcomes. PTK has its own characteristics characteristics that distinguish it from other research, including: the problems raised are problems faced by the teacher in the class and There is a goal to improve the teaching and learning process in the classroom. (Arikunto, S. (2007)

The method that will be used in this research is Classroom Action Research Classroom Action Research which is one of the problem solving strategies that utilizes real actions and processes. problem solving strategy that utilizes real action and the process of process of developing the ability to detect and solve problems. This research model is an R&H Classroom Action Research model which consists of four stages, namely: exploration, planning, action and observation, discussion. (Rosfiani, O., Hermawan, C. M.(2018)

Classroom action research is qualitative research although the data data collected can be quantitative, where the description is descriptive in the form of words. in the form of words, the researcher is the first instrument in data data collection, the process is as important as the product.(Kunandar, (2011)

Results and Discussion

The results of observations of the learning process of students in class X IPS 1 in the classroom, stating that most of the students have not participated or have not been involved in the learning process. Students tend to only listen to the teacher's explanation but do not focus and do not understand what is conveyed by the teacher, resulting in when students are given questions about related material, they cannot answer.

The action that will be taken by researchers to overcome this problem is by applying Kahoot learning media to the learning process:

Pre-cycle. This stage was carried out on January 16, 2023 which is known that the learning outcomes of Arabic language students in class X IPS 1 are still fairly unsatisfactory and have not reached the KKM. The factor that causes student learning outcomes is still low due to the lack of teacher innovation in using learning media that attracts students to learn.

The application of Kahoot game application-based assessment can help researchers or educators review students in the cognitive domain through the answer scores generated by students when answering quiz questions through the Kahoot game and train students to always develop knowledge in applying or applying the latest technology as the next generation.

Graph 1: Completeness of Student Learning Outcomes Pre-Phasic

From the graph above, it can be concluded that the percentage of completeness of students in taking the pre-cycle test with the Kahoot application as much as 47% and 52% who have not reached completeness.

**Graph 2:
Student Learning Outcomes Completion Cycle 1**

From the graph above, it can be concluded that the percentage of completeness of students in taking the cycle 1 test with the Kahoot application as much as 85% and 14% who have not reached completeness.

Graph 3: Diagram of Prasiklus and Cycle 1 Completion

Conclusion

To improve the learning outcomes of Arabic language students in class X IPS 1 at SMA Muhammadiyah Jakarta, researchers applied Kahoot game application-based assessment in the action of the class discussion learning model, in the learning process as an effort to overcome the lack of motivation and interest of students to follow learning, student inactivity in the learning process, and the absence of positive responses from students when learning takes place. The classroom action carried out by researchers consists of 2 cycles (pre-cycle and cycle 1) where each cycle applies Kahoot application game-based assessment with a Class Discussion learning model.

In the pre-cycle stage, researchers carried out the learning process using Kahoot game application-based assessment in Arabic language subjects on the topic of "science". It is known that at the pre-cycle stage, student learning outcomes are still fairly low, which is at 35% for students who are complete, and 64% for students who are not complete. So that from these learning outcomes it is stated that it has not reached the KKM. Therefore, researchers need to take further action, namely cycle 1.

At the cycle 1 stage, researchers carried out the learning process using Kahoot game application-based assessment in Arabic language subjects on the topic of "Science". It is known that at the cycle 1 stage, student learning outcomes have increased to 85% for students who are complete and 14% of students who have not completed the assessment.

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